

**THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF
CULTURAL COMPETENCE OF INTERPERSONAL COMMUNICATION**

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Methodology of TSPU named after Nizamiy

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Annotation: in this article, it can be seen what aspects should be paid attention to in the development of the competence of the culture of interpersonal communication in future teachers, a number of points of view on the theoretical foundations of the development of the competence of the culture of communication.

Keywords: personality, culture of communication, culture of interpersonal communication, competence, pedagogy, experience, education, communication, factor, teacher.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada bo'lajak o'qituvchilarda shaxslararo muloqot madaniyati kompetensiyasini rivojlantirishda qanday jihatlarga e'tibor qaratish kerakligi, muloqot madaniyati kompetensiyasini rivojlantirishning nazariy asoslari haqida bir qator fikrlar berilganligini ko'rish mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: Shaxs, muloqot madaniyati, shaxslararo muloqot madaniyati, kompetensiya, pedagogika, tajriba, ta'lim, muloqot, omil, o'qituvchi.

Аннотация: В данной статье можно увидеть, на какие аспекты следует обратить внимание при развитии компетентности культуры межличностного общения у будущих педагогов, дан ряд мнений о теоретических основах развития компетентности культуры общения.

Ключевые слова: личность, культура общения, культура межличностного общения, компетентность, педагогика, опыт, образование, общение, фактор, учитель.

The process of development and globalization puts urgent and modern demands on the state. To achieve high strategic goals, to occupy high positions in the world community, to achieve all-round well-being of society, the role of high-potential personnel and knowledgeable specialists is invaluable. In order to train such competitive personnel, it is necessary to carry out tasks such as increasing the knowledge and potential of the growing young generation, discovering their abilities.

As a result of the reforms carried out in our country, huge economic growth indicators are being achieved, increasing the demand for qualified personnel and advanced specialists in all fields. This in itself requires increasing the interest of our students in classes and increasing the attention of educators to

all-round education. The fact that the above requirements are very important for the educational system means that, as in most foreign countries, it is necessary to attract the best practices aimed at improving the quality of education by evaluating and monitoring the development of education and science.

This can be achieved through proper education, because properly implemented education makes a person intellectually and morally mature, in particular, a person fully respects the laws of nature and society. learns the truth and takes the right path in life, has the right relationship with others ¹.

In pedagogy, communication means the skill, method and system of interaction between the teacher and the student team, its essence, mutual information exchange, educational and educational influence, mutual interaction. is manifested in the achievement of understanding and has the following characteristics:

- communication is the most important professional tool in the educational activity of the teacher;
- social control and social laws are important to ensure proper implementation of the communication process;
- communication is considered the most important component of teacher-student relationship, and it plays the same important role as motivation in motivation;
- communication in pedagogy is the active organization of the teacher's interaction on the basis of influencing the students, the implementation of the planned function of a specific goal based on the program;
- communication - arises from the need for cooperation and is a multifaceted process of interpersonal relationship development;
- due to incorrect pedagogical communication, students develop fear and lack of confidence in their own strength, their attention and work activity decrease, the dynamics of speech is disturbed, and the ability to think independently and freely decreases.

The culture of interpersonal relations among future teachers is a professional relationship that allows the teacher to create a positive mental climate with students in class and extracurricular activities, creating the most comfortable psychological environment for him.

The main result of the close interaction of the teacher with the students:

- eliminate all processes that cause negative situations

¹ FOMirziyayeva "Formation of the culture of interpersonal communication in primary school students"-methodical guide., 2021

to give

- forming students' independent thinking skills;
- teach students to be active, to think freely, to express their opinions without fear and rely on them;
- development of hidden abilities of students;
- creating a mood of joy and happiness in class and extracurricular processes.

It is important to carry out experimental work in the implementation of pedagogical research works and in determining their effectiveness. For this purpose, a number of scientific works on the testing of scientific research works and the analysis of their results were studied and put into practice.

The purpose of the pedagogical experimental work is to conduct a theoretical analysis and experimental testing of the issue of the formation of a culture of interpersonal relations among future teachers. In the implementation of this goal and the organization of experimental work, methods of observation, questionnaires, interviews, control (test), and pedagogical experiments are used. During the pedagogical experiment-testing process, which is carried out in several stages, we determine the following main tasks:

1. In-depth analysis of the interpersonal culture of future teachers;
2. To study, compare, and analyze the level of the culture of interaction between the future teachers of the selected university using the questionnaire developed on the basis of the "Model of Interpersonal Relationship Culture in Future Teachers";
3. Summarizing the results of the experiment and giving analytical conclusions.

In the process of carrying out the research , experimental work is carried out at certain stages , and the determination of specific goals and tasks at each stage of the research has an effective effect on obtaining the expected results . Based on this conclusion, experimental work is organized in the following stages:

1. Determining stage:

In this:

- interview and questionnaire methods are used to determine the knowledge, skills and abilities of future school teachers to develop the culture of interpersonal relations.
- In order to observe the actual state of interpersonal culture of future teachers, interviews and observations were conducted and critically analyzed with future teachers in class and extracurricular situations.
- The problems that arise in interpersonal relations among future teachers were studied, and pedagogical diagnostic methods "blitz-survey method", "testing

method" method of performing situational tasks are used among future teachers.

- In addition, the "questionnaire" method is used to determine the interpersonal relationship among future teachers.

2. Formative stage.

- Scientific-methodical and practical recommendations on the development of interpersonal culture in future teachers will be introduced to students through lectures and trainings.

- Collaborative events will be held on the topic "The importance of age characteristics in the process of interpersonal relations", "Father and mother - the basis of relations" on the formation of the culture of interpersonal relations among future teachers.

- At the formative stage, methods such as "Labyrinth", "Fan", "Problem", "Discussion", "KBI" are used in order for future teachers to work as a team and enter into interpersonal relations with each other.

3. Summarizing stage.

At the generalization stage, the methods of "Analysis of Concepts", "Assessment", and SWOT analysis are used in order to strengthen the acquired knowledge and skills of future teachers, analyze and evaluate the results.

At the generalization stage, experimental work and obtained results are analyzed. At this stage, the selected test subjects are divided into experimental and control groups from prospective teachers.

It is possible to see many disorders in the child's relationship with people through a simple observation during the analysis of interpersonal relationships in future teachers. We can observe future teachers avoiding communication with their peers or constant conflicts, fights, and complaints arising between them. However, without observations, it is difficult to clarify the factors and reasons that caused these problems, and without knowing them, the result of trying to help future teachers will be zero. It is necessary to use various tests to analyze these reasons for avoiding interpersonal relations and communication.

In order to study the interpersonal relations of the future teachers in our research work, the sociometric method is conducted in the test group. In order to study the communication of students with friends of the same age, to study their place and position in the group, he used the type of sociometric method called "Sociometry". This methodology is aimed at studying interpersonal relations, communication, and behavior issues in a group of prospective teachers, using a mask that expresses a good or bad mood drawn on paper to the

members of the experimental group, representing the desire to isolate themselves from leadership and obedience. consists of transfer.

methodology is carried out in a pilot group of future teachers. After that, the results were analyzed in terms of quantity and quality . At the end of the methodology, the results of the quantitative analysis are shown in tables and diagrams.

A list of medicines:

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